

AIRBUS DAMAGE TOLERANCE METHODOLOGIES FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

This is an overview of the damage tolerance approaches and methodologies used for the design, certification and maintenance of composite structures at Airbus. It covers impact threat, damage detectability, inspection program, fatigue, tests and analyses. It is intended to provide directions for future research in the area of composite damage tolerance.

Keywords: Damage Tolerance, Impact, Composites, Detectability, Aircraft

DAMAGE TOLERANCE APPROACH

The starting point for setting the DT (damage tolerance) philosophy is the regulation which consists of requirements defined by the airworthiness authorities. Policies for means of compliance are defined by interpreting the requirements.

Impact Threat

Impact threat is defined by analysing damage data recorded in service. The threat is different depending on the location of the aircraft. Large amount of data covering long enough service time and large enough fleet size is essential for producing statistically significant impact threat.

Damage Detectability

Damage detectability is represented by BVID (Barely Visible Impact Damage). It is dependent on the type of inspection and is determined by analysis of detectability test data. BVID is defined for transverse impact and edge impact.

Inspection programs

Determined using a probabilistic analysis taking into account impact threat, probability of detection, load occurrence, residual strength variation, etc.

Large Damage Capability

Design precautions to protect the aircraft against unknown events.

Manufacturing Defects

Allowable manufacturing defects are established through quality assurance plan and have to be accounted for in the static strength demonstration.

Fatigue

There should be no initiation of new damage and no growth of existing damages (BVID or large damages) under repeated loading. The number of cycles to be justified depends on the type of damage. Test and analysis are used to meet this requirement.

TEST PYRAMID AND ANALYSIS

Building block test approach is used, as shown in the figure below.

Transverse Impact Analysis

An empirical method that predicts damage size, dent depth and residual strength for compression, tension and shear. Method accounts for material difference, laminate thickness, lay-up and stacking sequence, hot/wet effect, scatter (B-value), etc. Requirements and plans for next generation method and tools.

Edge Impact Analysis

Design allowables derived from tests to cover stringer top edge impact and skin edge impact. (e.g. hole edge). It is recommended to develop research activities to investigate concepts for improved edge impact resistance and methods for analysing edge impact structures.